

Histopathological Differences in Rectal Cancer between Patient (≤ 50 Years Age) and (>50 Years Age): a Tertiary Care Cancer Center Experience in Odisha.

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Abstract:

Introduction: Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most commonly diagnosed cancer. Recent data from Western and Asian countries have shown an increase in the number of CRC cases among patients under the screening age of 50 with late stage presentation leading to poor survival.

Aim and Objectives: To analyze the pattern of histopathological presentation in rectal cancer between patients younger than 50 years old and older than 50 years age.

Material & Method: This hospital based retrospective study was conducted on patients who histopathologically diagnosed rectal cancer and came to Department of Medical Oncology, AHPGIC, Cuttack for their management over a period of five years from January 2019 to December 2023. The histopathological details of patients were collected and compared between <50 and >50 years age.

Results: During the study period, a total of 84 rectal cancer patients were encountered. Out of included cases, males were predominated 43(51%) with a male to female ratio of 1:1. The majority of patients were between the ages of 41 to 50 years old. Younger age patients had more aggressive disease in terms of advanced stage disease at presentation and poorly differentiated tumors; 53.6% patients had T3/T4 disease and 53.6% patients with poorly differentiated tumors in contrast to patients with age more than 50 years.

Conclusion: This study found a higher number of younger rectal cancer patients (under 50 years old). These younger patients also tended to have more aggressive tumors or be in a later stage of the disease. To improve the situation, we need a combined effort (multi-sectorial approach) based on strong evidence. This should focus on catching rectal cancer early and giving the best treatment (effective management) possible.

Key word: Rectal cancer, Younger age, aggressive tumor type, Adenocarcinoma.

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Introduction

Globally, colorectal cancer (CRC) ranks third in new diagnoses and second in cancer deaths. It makes up a significant portion of the global cancer burden, with 19.3 million new cases and almost 10 million deaths annually. This translates to 10% of all new cancers and 9.4% of cancer deaths worldwide. While CRC incidence rates place it 16th overall, India specifically reported roughly 60,000 new cases and 39,000 deaths of rectal cancer in 2020. These numbers are expected to climb to 110,000 new cases and 64,000 deaths by 2040 [1,2].

Catching pre-cancerous growths early through colonoscopies dramatically reduces colorectal cancer (CRC) cases and deaths [3]. Traditionally, CRC was seen as an older adult disease, typically appearing after 50[4]. As a result, most advisory committees worldwide recommended screening

between 50 and 75 years old [5]. However, recent data from Western and Asian countries shows a concerning rise in CRC cases among younger people, those who wouldn't qualify for the old screening age [6, 7]. This new information prompted the US Preventive Services Task Force to update their guidelines, recommending CRC screening begins at 45 instead of 50[8]. Additionally, research suggests younger patients are often diagnosed with more advanced and aggressive forms of CRC, leading to poorer survival rates. Furthermore, studies also suggest that young age is associated with more advanced stages of the disease at diagnosis and with more aggressive histopathological characteristics leading to poor survival [9].

While most research points to a poorer prognosis for younger CRC patients, a small number of studies suggest outcomes might be similar or even better compared to those diagnosed later [10]. The impact of CRC and its treatment on younger patients' fertility, lifespan, and overall well-being makes understanding their prognosis crucial [11].

While several studies across India have investigated the epidemiology and clinical features of rectal cancer, none have focused specifically on our state, Odisha. We believe basic descriptive studies offer valuable real-world data to improve our understanding of this disease and develop strategies to lessen its burden, morbidity, and mortality in developing countries. Therefore, this study aimed to assess and compare the clinical and pathological characteristics of rectal cancer patients diagnosed before and after the age of 50.

Material & Methods

This hospital based retrospective study was conducted on patients who histopathologically diagnosed rectal cancer and came to Department of Medical Oncology, AHPGIC, Cuttack for their management over a period of five years from January 2019 to December 2023.

Inclusion: The study included all biopsy-proven primary rectal carcinoma patients.

Exclusion: Patients receiving previous chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy and those with histology other than carcinoma were excluded from the study cohort. Patients with incomplete

clinicopathological data were also excluded from this study.

Patient's demographic and clinicopathological features were retrieved from medical record section. Parameters studied included age, sex, site of lesion, clinical presentations, duration of symptoms, histopathological parameters (tumor type, tumor grade, tumor stage, lymphovascular invasion status, perineural invasion status, lymph node status, and stage of the disease. The histological subtypes and grades of carcinoma were assigned based on the WHO's classification. The cancer stage at the initial diagnosis was defined according to the 7th edition of American Joint Committee on Cancer TNM staging system.

Patient's demographic and clinicopathological features were compared between the two age groups ≤ 50 and >50 years). Numerical variables were expressed as mean (SD) while categorical data was summarized as frequency (%). Chi-square was used to compare the frequency of all variables between the two age groups. P-value < 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results:

During the study period, a total of 84 rectal cancer patients were included. Among the included cases, males were predominant, with 43 (51.19%) patients, resulting in a male to female ratio of 1:1. The majority of patients (24, or 28.57%) were between the ages of 41-50 years old. Forty-eight (57%) patients were less than 50 years old (Table 1).

Table 1: Age & Sex distribution of total rectal cancer patients.

Age Groups	Male (N=43)	Female (N=41)	Total (N=84)
0-10	-	-	-
11-20	1 (2.32%)	-	1 (1.19%)
21-30	5 (11.62%)	3 (7.31%)	8 (9.52%)
31-40	5 (11.62%)	10 (24.39%)	15 (17.85%)
41-50	13 (30.23%)	11 (26.82%)	24 (28.57%)
51-60	8 (18.6%)	12 (29.26%)	20 (23.8%)
61-70	7 (16.72%)	2 (4.87%)	9 (10.71%)
71-80	2 (4.65%)	2 (4.87%)	4 (4.76%)
>81	2 (4.65%)	1 (2.43%)	3 (3.57%)

Overall 69 (82%) patients experienced a change in bowel habit along with bleeding per rectum and 68(81.0) patients reported a change in bowel habits along with weight loss as a primary symptom to visit a physician for treatment. The average duration of presenting complaints was 6.4 months. Among the

patients, 18(21.4%) had less than 3 months, 36(42.9%) had symptoms for 3–6 months, 21(25.0%) for 6 months to 1 year and 9(10.7%) for more than 1 year. Majority of the patients 42 (50.0%) had a low-lying rectal cancer with anal canal involvement. (Table 2).

Table 2: Comparative analysis of gender and clinical presentation of young and old rectal cancer patients.

Variables		Total (N=84)		≤50 year age (N=48)		≥51 year age (N=36)		P value
		n	%	n	%	n	%	
Sex	Male	43	51.2	24	50.0	19	52.8	0.8
	Female	41	48.8	24	50.0	17	47.2	
Symptoms	Bleeding	69	82.0	13	27.1	16	44.4	0.7
	Loss of appetite	68	81.0	30	62.5	22	61.1	
	Weight loss	57	67.9	21	43.7	22	61.1	
	Abdominal pain	61	72.6	21	43.7	19	52.8	
	Discharge	12	14.3	4	8.3	9	25.0	
	Incontinence	24	28.6	13	27.1	11	30.6	
	Obstruction	11	13.1	7	14.6	9	25.0	
	Perforation	13	15.5	7	14.6	6	16.7	
Duration of symptoms	<3 months	18	21.4	11	22.9	7	19.4	0.1
	3–6 months	36	42.9	22	45.8	14	38.9	
	6–12 months	21	25.0	8	16.7	14	38.9	
	>12 months	9	10.7	3	6.3	6	16.7	
Tumor location	High	14	16.7	8	16.7	6	16.7	0.8
	Middle	28	33.3	15	31.3	13	36.1	
	Lower	42	50.0	25	52.1	17	47.2	

Conventional invasive adenocarcinoma was the most common histology seen in 66(78.6%) of the patients. Most of the patients (40.62%) had a grade I tumor. LVI and PNI positive was observed in 39 (46.4%) and 24 (28.6%) cases respectively. Fourty five (53.6%) had T3/T4 disease and 43 (51.2%) had N2 disease (Table 3).

Stage III was the most common presenting stage in 52 (61.9%) patients, followed by 29(34.5%) and 3 (3.5%) patients with stage II and IV, respectively. In patients with stage IV disease, the most common site of distant metastases was liver, followed by peritoneal.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of histopathological parameters between young and old rectal cancer patients

Histopathological characteristics		Total (N=84)		≤50 year age (N=48)		≥51 year age (N=36)		P value
		n	%	n	%	n	%	
Histological type	Conventional adenocarcinoma	66	78.6	34	70.8	32	88.9	0.1
	Adenocarcinoma with Mucinous components	11	13.1	8	16.7	3	8.3	
	Adenocarcinoma with signet ring cell components	7	8.3	6	12.5	1	2.8	
Grade	1 (Well differentiated)	13	15.5	9	18.8	4	11.1	0.5
	2 (Moderately differentiated)	26	31.0	16	33.3	10	27.8	
	3 (Poorly differentiated)	45	53.6	33	68.8	12	33.3	
LVSI	Positive	39	46.4	23	47.9	16	44.4	0.7
	Negative	45	53.6	25	52.1	20	55.6	
PNI	Positive	24	28.6	14	29.2	10	27.8	0.8
	Negative	60	71.4	34	70.8	26	72.2	
Tumor stage	T1-T2	39	46.4	19	39.5	20	55.5	0.1
	T3-T4	45	53.6	29	60.4	16	44.4	
Node stage	N0	45	53.6	22	45.8	23	63.9	0.2
	N1	43	51.2	26	54.2	17	47.2	
	N2	26	31.0	13	27.1	13	36.1	

A comparative analysis of young onset rectal cancer patients (age <50 years) versus older rectal cancer patients (age ≥50 years) showed a slightly higher male preponderance in the older age group. Around 52% of the patients in the younger age group had the

disease in the lower rectum involving anal canal as compared to 47% in the older age group, but the difference was not statistically significant. Young age patients had more aggressive disease in terms of advance stage disease at presentation and poorly

differentiated tumors; 64% patients had T3/T4 disease and 68.8% patients with poorly differentiated tumors in contrast to patients with age more than 50 years.

Discussion:

The researchers looked at rectal cancer patients and how their disease appeared and behaved depending on their age at diagnosis. There were slightly more men than women in their study, which is similar to other research on colorectal cancer [6]. The exact reason for this difference isn't fully known, but another study suggests it might be due to men and women having different exposures to risk factors like diet and lifestyle (such as drinking alcohol and eating red meat) or because hormones and other receptors affect the colon and rectum differently in men and women [12]

Studies reveal a striking difference in the percentage of young people diagnosed with rectal cancer depending on location. While a Canadian study found only 3.36% of patients under 45 [13], studies from the USA, Sudan, and India reported much higher rates, ranging from 11.3% to 43.84% for patients under 45 or 50 [14, 15, 16, 17]. This significant variation across countries strengthens the idea that geography might play a role in how often or how rectal cancer manifests in younger individuals. Our own findings, showing a similar proportion of young patients, further support this theory.

Scientists have done a lot of research on how rectal cancer develops (pathogenesis). This research suggests several factors might be involved, including different genes. These genes may help us understand the steps involved in rectal cancer development (pathways). Some of these steps include chromosomal instability (changes in chromosome structure) and hypermethylation of the MLH1 gene promoter (a change that reduces the activity of a gene important for DNA repair) [18].

While genetics might seem like a cause for early rectal cancer, only 17% of patients had a family history of any kind of cancer [17]. This suggests family history might not be a reliable way to assess someone's risk of getting rectal cancer young. Early detection is crucial for better outcomes in cancer, but in our study, over half (53%) had advanced tumors and most (62%) had lymph node spread at diagnosis. Furthermore, the lack of family history, combined with young patients' sometimes poor response to treatment, emphasizes the urgent need for national programs to find and treat these patients early.

Our study found that most rectal cancers were in the lower rectum, near the anus. This is similar to other studies in India, such as one by Patil et al. [19] which found that over half (54%) of their patients had rectal cancer near the anus, and another by Laskar et

al. [20] which also reported a higher prevalence of rectal tumors in the lower area.

Young rectal cancer patients often experience belly pain, bleeding, reduced appetite, and weight loss. Some even have emergencies like blockages or holes in their intestines. Studies show rectal bleeding is most common (almost 90%), followed by pain and bowel changes [17]. Young patients seem to have more bleeding, pain, blockages, and holes compared to older ones. This might be because the disease acts faster in younger people or because they wait longer to see a doctor. On average, young patients wait over 11 months with symptoms, compared to 9.6 months for older patients. Our study finds a longer wait time than another one in India [19]. Our study found younger rectal cancer patients were more likely to have advanced stage III disease compared to older patients. This could be due to Lack of widespread screening programs and timely access to medical care might contribute to delayed diagnoses [23]. Less likely to suspect cancer in younger patients due to the generally lower incidence in this age group. This could lead to misdiagnosis and delays in getting the right treatment. And in our region, younger patients are often initially treated for other conditions like amoebiasis, granulomatous infections, or worm infestations, further delaying a CRC diagnosis. Early stage CRC often has no symptoms, and these cases are typically found during screening which isn't common in our country. This explains why our study found mostly advanced stage presentations.

Our study, like others before it [11, 20, 21], found adenocarcinoma to be the main type of cancer in both young and old patients. However, the younger group had a much higher proportion of tumors that were poorly differentiated, meaning they looked less like healthy tissue. This aligns with research by Ghodssi-Ghassemabadi et al [9] who also found poorer tumor quality in younger patients. While not as statistically strong, our study also suggests younger patients might have a higher chance of having adenocarcinomas with signet ring features, which can indicate a more aggressive cancer [24].

Conclusion:

This study found a higher number of younger rectal cancer patients (under 50 years old). These younger patients also tended to have more aggressive tumors or be in a later stage of the disease. To improve the situation, we need a combined effort (multi-sectorial approach) based on strong evidence. This should focus on catching rectal cancer early and giving the best treatment (effective management) possible.

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